

Sexual Satisfaction as a Factor of Psychological Well-Being

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Abstract: *The concept of “satisfaction with one’s own sexual life” gives a new impetus to the study of psychological well-being of an individual in general and success in professional activity of businessmen in particular as components of personal maturity, positive sanogenic personal potential. The article presents modern works of foreign and domestic scientists on the problems of human sexuality (biological, medical and sexological, general psychological and other aspects); well-being of an individual. The main aspects of the problem of satisfaction with one’s own sexual life as sexual well-being of an individual and the problems of psychological well-being of an individual are considered. Research assumptions are formulated. The theoretical and methodological basis of the study of the problem of satisfaction with one’s own sexual life in the context of psychological well-being of businessmen is determined. The results of a theoretical and empirical study of the current psychological problem of the interrelationship between satisfaction with one’s own sexual life with psychological well-being of modern domestic businessmen are presented. Proof of the interrelationship between sexual satisfaction with the psychological well-being of businessmen was carried out using Pearson, Tau-b Kendall and Spearman correlation analyses and the results were presented. Positive rather high correlations, which are revealed by three types of correlation analysis, enable to state that psychological well-being of businesspeople depends on their sexual development and their satisfaction with their sexual lives.*

Keywords: *sexuality of an individual, sexual attitudes, sexual satisfaction, sexual well-being, sexual permissibility, sexual fulfillment, business success.*

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Introduction

Professional business activities are associated with high rates of change, financial risk, lack of time and information, take place in conditions of uncertainty and fierce competition. All this requires from businessmen special personal and professional qualities: non-standard volitional decisions and actions, business intuition, stress resistance, emotional and volitional regulation, ability to build necessary interpersonal relationships, management of different groups of people (Chernyavskaya, 2010; Cherniavska, 2021; Palamarchuk, 2020; Nerubasska, Palshkov, & Maksymchuk, 2020; Nerubasska, Maksymchuk, 2020; Gerasymova, 2019).

New approaches to educating businessmen are based on priority of personal qualities such as initiative and empathy. That is, the ability to empathize, adapt and persuade. It is these abilities that are necessary for success in professional business, which in turn contributes to psychological well-being of businessmen.

On the other hand, psychological well-being of businessmen is affected by their positive emotional state, necessary for effective business activities, associated with satisfaction with their sexual life, with fulfillment of the sexual sphere and harmony in sexual relations with a sexual partner and harmonious family relationships.

Modern studies of the phenomenon of sexuality are widely represented in foreign and domestic scientific literature, first of all, the following aspects:

- biological factors of sex and sexual behavior of humans (Pfaus, Scepkowski, Marson & Georgiadis, 2014);
- medical and sexological (Domoratsky, 2009; Kocharyan, 2007; Roach, 2017);
- general psychological (Ainsworth & Bauermeister, 2012; Bass, 2017; Laumann, Nicolosi, 2005; Tolman, Diamond, Bauermeister, George, Pfaus & Ward, 2014);
- sexuality and love (Kernberg, 2000; Martel, 2006; Roach, 2017).

Research is devoted to certain types of well-being of an individual and related concepts, such as:

- happiness (Lyubomirski, 2014; Ryan, Deci, 2001; Seligman, 2013);
- psychological well-being (Byers, Rehman, 2014; Diener, 2009; Diener, Wirtz, Tov, Kim-Prieto, 2010; Zasekina, Mastruk, 20017; Kahneman, Diener, Schwarz, 1999; Stephenson, Meston, 2015; Ryff, Keyes, 1995; Seligman, 2013; Chernyavskaya, 2021);

- sexual well-being (Hupalovska, 2019; Chalova, 2016; Stephenson, Meston, 2015);

- sexual health (Mulhall, Incrocci, Goldstein, Rosen, 2011).

The immediacy of solving the problem of interrelationship of satisfaction with one's own sexual life and psychological well-being of businessmen is due to the problems that accompany real business activities and private life of businessmen, such as stress reactions, psychological maladaptation and emotional burnout of businessmen in crisis, uncertainty and constant changes as well as deterioration of psychological well-being of businessmen due to extreme nature of their professional activities, which can negatively affect personal and family life of businessmen, which can lead to sexual disharmony, namely disharmonious interpersonal relationships with a sexual partner, and can also negatively influence interpersonal relationships with other people.

Finding ways to strengthen training of businessmen (business owners and partners) and providing them with necessary psychological support, which is associated with emotional and empathic competence, formation and development of abilities to harmonize own sexual relationships to achieve psychological well-being of businessmen.

General research assumptions

1. A high level of sexual well-being development of businessmen has a positive effect on their personal business success.

2. With a certain allowance for the specific nature of the topic, we can assume that a person's sexual behavior is influenced by the same key factors (fulfillment and satisfaction with own sexual life, libido, responsibility in interpersonal relationships) as business success (personal significance and satisfaction with business activities, energy resources, responsibility for their decisions and actions, ...). Therefore, highly developed components of sexual well-being have a positive effect on the development of business success components.

3. Sexual well-being of a person is highly (medium, low) formed at high (medium, low) indicators of two methods: 1) method of "Sexual attitudes" by Eisenko by the indicators "Sexual Satisfaction" and "Fulfillment"; 2) method of "Psychological well-being" by Riff by the indicator "Psychological well-being".

The **objective of the article** is theoretical and empirical analysis of interrelationship between satisfaction with one's own sexual life and psychological well-being of businessmen.

Modern research on the problem of psychological well-being

Despite the primary importance of sexual satisfaction of the individual not only in married relations, but also for the success of doing business, this relationship refers to understudied psychologic phenomena. Facts used in research and psychotherapeutic practice are based only on describing disorders in the sexual sphere, but the problem of interrelationship between satisfaction with one's sexual life and psychological well-being of businessmen is insufficiently studied both in theoretical and practical aspects, because in the process of training businessmen this problem is not given due attention. Main attention is paid to professional training of businessmen, and such components of personal maturity, positive sanogenic potential of an individual as emotional competence, sexual-harmonious relationships, psychological well-being are not given enough attention.

The phenomenon of subjective well-being of the individual is fully studied and researched in world psychological science, first of all, in connection with the study of states of optimal functioning of a human. These phenomena describe a holistic psychological reality, its versatility that is reflected in the methodological traditions of the research of well-being, peculiarities of its conceptualization, and therefore in its meaningful, content, etc. characteristics (Kamsheko, Traverse, 2020).

It should be noted that in recent decades more and more attention is paid to the problem of satisfaction with one's own sexual life as a person's sexual well-being (Ainsworth, Baumeister, 2012; Bass, 2017; Byers, Rehman, 2014; Hupalovska, 2019; Mulhall, Incrocci, Goldstein, Rosen, 2011; Stephenson, Meston, 2015; Chalova, 2016).

Thus, Ainsworth and Baumeister (2012) study sexual transformations related to time, relationships, and sociocultural context; Bass (2017) studies the evolutionary aspect of sexual desire and strategies for finding sexual partners; Byers and Rehman (2014) consider sexual satisfaction and sexual self-fulfillment in relationships; Hupalovska (2019) studies sexual well-being as a factor of subjective well-being of a person, exploring sexual scenarios by which people organize and evaluate their sexual life; Chalova (2016) investigates sexual well-being in stable married couples; Stephenson and Meston (2015) in their study confirmed a strong link between sexual well-being and overall life satisfaction; in studies of sexual relations and behavior of different groups of population, scientists have proven that for people of different ages (40 to 80 years) (Laumann, Nicolosi, 2005), and for people of different health conditions, (cancer

patients, etc.) (Mulhall, Incrocci, Goldstein, Rosen, 2011) sexuality retains its significance even in the context of serious health problems.

Modern research on the problem of psychological well-being, happiness is presented in the works of scientists such as Byers, Rehman (2014); Diener (2009); Diener, Wirtz, Tov, Kim-Prieto (2010); Zasekina, Maistruk (2017); Kahneman, Diener, Schwarz (1999); Lyubomirski (2014); Stephenson, Meston (2015); Ryff, Keyes (1995); Ryan, Deci (2001); Seligman (2013); Chernyavska (2021).

Kahneman, Diener, Schwarz (1999) study well-being from a hedonistic point of view; Zasekina and Maistruk (2017) study psychological well-being of an individual in the context of unconditional acceptance of oneself; Kernberg (2000) studies specifics of love relationships as norms and pathologies; new approaches to study of the phenomenon of happiness and satisfaction were presented by Ryan and Deci (2001); Lyubomirski (2014); Martel (2006); Seligman (2009); new measures to assess well-being, prosperity and positive and negative feelings are studied by Diener, Wirtz, Tov, Kim-Prieto (2010); Chernyavskaya (2021) studies well-being and success of an individual in the context of human orthobiosis.

Based on their own vision of the place and role of the phenomena of sexual satisfaction and psychological well-being in the structure of personal maturity, personal potential, researchers propose main components of the structure and approaches to development of sexual satisfaction-fulfillment and psychological well-being of an individual.

It should be noted that modern professional training of future managers and business representatives should have such disciplines in their arsenal, which will help them in capturing and practical application of emotional and communicative competence and their psychological compensatory mechanisms that will help not only in professional activity, which will contribute to harmonization of sexual relationships to improve psychological well-being of businessmen, which contributes to business success.

Study of the interrelationship between satisfaction with one's own sexual life and psychological well-being of businessmen

Psychological well-being, as a whole, is associated with personal, professional and social variables. It is as an image and categorical structure in individual consciousness of a person, permanently leads to new aspects of their experience, which is reflected in numerous studies. Psychological well-being is "evaluated" by the person themselves from the standpoint of their values and goals. Since the latter are always individual, then there cannot be

universal ones for all structures of psychological well-being. In this case, it is advisable to study factors that influence the subjective sense of satisfaction (existential experience, attitude towards one's own life, sexual satisfaction) (Serdyuk, 2017, p.130).

From the specified factors, a special role in the psychological well-being of the business community representatives is played by their sexual satisfaction (Holmberg et al, 2010; Hooghe, 2012). In the long-term development in males, sexual satisfaction allows estimate health condition and physical intimacy (Heiman et al, 2011). A higher level of sexual satisfaction is associated with a lower level of depression and anxiety in females (Frohlich, Meston, 2002; Tower, Krasner, 2006). Thus, it is difficult to overestimate the contribution of a sexual component to overall satisfaction with professional activities.

At the same time, the psychological importance of this indicator contrasts sharply with the degree of methodological development of the construct of sexual satisfaction in family, age and clinical psychology. In the twentieth century, the issues of sexual satisfaction and its influence on the psychological well-being of the individual were given very insufficient attention of scientists, and the psychoanalysis, which claimed a leading role in understanding of this sphere, mostly avoided traditional scientific study and did not contribute to the development of special measuring instruments. At the same time as a result of the Sexual Revolution of the 1950's and 60's in America and Europe, the vacuum methodological tools began to quickly fill with social workers, sexologists and other clinicians (Breslav, 2013, p. 25). Starting from this period, clinicians in the first place, faced a significant number of cases of sexual disorders and problems that lead to a decrease in psychological well-being, especially representatives of the business environment, their emotional burnout at work and reduction of efficiency in professional activity.

The reasons for this lie in the fact that business activity can be interpreted as a kind of behaviour in a hostile social environment, due to the crucial differences of the interests of private business and society. Moreover, these differences begin not only from the level of subjective assessments, but are rooted in the very essence of entrepreneurship: in its initial principles - innovation and aspiration for personal success - there is already a threat to stability, the formed and habitual order of things for the majority of the population (Ermolayeva, 2014, p. 564). Permanent exposure of businessmen to a hostile social environment leads to stress, and long stress, in turn, becomes a cause of emotional burnout, which negatively affects sexual function and is the cause of psychological discomfort. In order to determine

whether a businessman is in a state of emotional burnout, and to identify the stage of it, a specialist consultation is required, during which they will conduct testing, using, for example, a Boyko test, or similar tools.

We believe that simultaneously with testing for emotional burnout of business environment representatives, it is necessary to apply psychodiagnostic techniques to them as well, to determine the impact of the sexual component on psychological well-being of businessmen.

Such techniques have been applied since 1966, when the Thorne sexual questionnaire was issued, consisting of 200 points for the diagnosis of sexual psychopathology (Thorne, 1966). Following this questionnaire there were many methods of psychodiagnostics of sexual life - from small aimed at studying separate types of sexual life disorders (Lopiccolo, Steger, 1974) to multidimensional DSFI (DeRogatis Sexual Functioning Inventory; Derogatis, Melisaratos, 1979), consisting of 8 subscales and 247 points. However, there is still no questionnaire aimed at the diagnosis of sexual satisfaction and psychological well-being, and the few existing techniques do not allow to form a full idea of this mutual influence.

In special literature one can find only five techniques that are more or less aimed at solving this task. These include a scale of sexual satisfaction for Women by Whitley and Poulsen (SSS-W; Whitley, Poulsen, 1975) comprising 32 and 23 points, as well as a scale with the same name by Meston and Trapnell, consisting of 30 statements with a five-point agree-disagree scale; clinical questionnaire of sexual satisfaction by Golombok and Rust of 28 points (Rust, Golombok, 1985); Index of Sexual Satisfaction (ISS) of 25 points; as well as The Global Measure of Sexual Satisfaction (GMSEX, p. 27)

However, all these techniques give a very approximate idea of the characteristics of this phenomenon, since only the overall modality of the attitude to this sphere of life of an individual is practically evaluated, leaving all its most important components in the shadows, including psychological well-being.

The theoretical and methodological analysis of the most well-known foreign and domestic studies on sexual well-being problems and the personal success in business conducted by us, allowed to determine the two most progressive, from our point of view, psychodiagnostic methods: a questionnaire of attitudes to sex (Eisenk); psychological well-being questionnaire (Ryff). Using these instruments of psychoanalysis, let's conduct an empirical analysis of the relationship of satisfaction with one's own sexual life and psychological well-being of businessmen.

The following businessmen were studied: entrepreneurs-beginners (n = 50); mid-level managers (n = 70); top managers and business owners (n = 30).

To prove interrelationship between sexual satisfaction and psychological well-being of businessmen, we conducted Pearson, Tau-b Kendall and Spearman correlation analyses using the statistical program SPSS 26.0 for Windows XP. Table 1 presents the results of Pearson correlation analysis.

Table 1. Pearson correlation analysis results

Pearson correlation		Permissibility	Fulfillment	Sexual satisfaction	Psychological well-being
Permissibility	Pearson correlation	1	.502**	.525**	.538**
	Value (two-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.538
	N	150	150	150	150
Fulfillment	Pearson correlation	.502**	1	.881**	.842**
	Value (two-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.549
	N	150	150	150	150
Sexual satisfaction	Pearson correlation	.525**	.881**	1	.843**
	Value (two-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.548
	N	150	150	150	150
Psychological well-being	Pearson correlation	.538**	.842**	.843**	1
	Value (two-tailed)	0.322	0.549	0.548	
	N	150	150	150	150

*Note: Pearson's correlation analysis: ** Correlation is significant at the level of 0.01 (2-tailed); * Correlation is significant at the level of 0.05 (2-tailed).*

The table shows only the significant part of the correlation analysis, as all calculations obtained using the program SPSS 26.0 for Windows XP cannot be presented.

According to the results of correlation analysis, it is possible to note that correlation coefficient of the level of strength of psychological well-being, which according to the psychological well-being questionnaire (Ryff) reflects the general indicator of psychological well-being of businessmen and

indicates their personal success, has sufficient positive connections with some subscales of the questionnaire of attitudes to sex (Eisenk) such as: “Permissibility”, “Fulfillment” and “Sexual satisfaction”.

A sufficient positive relationship ($r > 0.538$) between the general indicator of psychological well-being and the subscale “Permissibility” indicates that modern and easy attitude of the surveyed businessmen to sex contributes to formation of their stable psychological well-being.

There is a strong positive direct relationship ($r > 0.842$) between overall psychological well-being indicator and the “Fulfillment” subscale, confirming our assumption that satisfaction with one’s sexual life is an extremely attractive condition for most people as part of their psychological well-being.

Sexual satisfaction is also one of the components of psychological well-being, which is proved by sufficient positive relationship ($r > 0.538$) according to the Pearson correlation between these indicators. Table 2 presents results of the Kendall’s Tau-b correlation analysis.

Table 2. Kendall’s Tau-b correlation analysis results

Tau-b Kendall		Permissibility	Fulfillment	Sexual satisfaction	Psychological well-being
Permissibility	Correlation coefficient	1.000	.373**	.418**	.595**
	Value (two-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.546
	N	150	150	150	150
Fulfillment	Correlation coefficient	.373**	1.000	.763**	.714**
	Value (two-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.751
	N	150	150	150	150
Sexual satisfaction	Correlation coefficient	.418**	.763**	1.000	.518**
	Value (two-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.599
	N	150	150	150	150
Psychological well-being	Correlation coefficient	.595**	.714**	.518**	1.000
	Value (two-tailed)	0.546	0.751	0.599	
	N	150	150	150	150

*Note: Kendall’s Tau-b: ** Correlation is significant at the level of 0.01 (2-tailed); * Correlation is significant at the level of 0.05 (2-tailed).*

When analyzing the matrix, it is possible to note that direct significant relations were found on all selected subscales of the questionnaire of attitudes to sex (Eisenk) and the general indicator of psychological well-being according to the corresponding questionnaire. Thus, the levels on the subscale “Permissibility” and the subscale “Sexual Satisfaction” are significantly positively correlated with the general indicator of psychological well-being ($\tau = 0.595$ and $\tau = 0.518$, respectively). A direct positive significant correlation was found between the subscale “Fulfillment” and the indicator of psychological well-being ($\tau = 0.714$).

Between the subscales of the questionnaire of attitudes to sex (Eisenk) quite positive correlations are also found, which indicates that with a normal easy attitude to sex, general satisfaction with own sexual life a person is able to fulfill their sexual needs, which becomes one of the components of psychological well-being formation. Table 3 presents results of Spearman’s correlation analysis.

Table 3. Spearman’s correlation analysis results

Spearman’s Rho		Permissibility	Fulfillment	Sexual satisfaction	Psychological well-being
Permissibility	Correlation coefficient	1.000	.474**	.538**	.497**
	Value (two-tailed)		0.000	0.000	0.489
	N	150	150	150	150
Fulfillment	Correlation coefficient	.474**	1.000	.879**	.743**
	Value (two-tailed)	0.000		0.000	0.759
	N	150	150	150	150
Sexual satisfaction	Correlation coefficient	.538**	.879**	1.000	.622**
	Value (two-tailed)	0.000	0.000		0.658
	N	150	150	150	150
Psychological well-being	Correlation coefficient	.497**	.743**	.622**	1.000
	Value (two-tailed)	0.489	0.759	0.658	
	N	150	150	150	150

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the level of 0.01

*. Correlation is significant at the level of 0.05

To conduct further factor analysis of the results and prove the hypothesis of the interrelation between sexual well-being of businessmen and their personal business success, using the static program SPSS 26.0 for Windows XP, we calculated the Spearman rank correlation.

According to the obtained results (Tables 1 – 3) it was found that all selected subscales from the questionnaire of attitudes to sex (Eisenk) and the general scale of psychological well-being of the questionnaire of psychological well-being (Ryff) revealed significant correlations ($-1 \leq p \leq 1$). That is, the correlation between the two values is close to one, and Spearman's correlation coefficient is positive for all selected subscales: "Permissibility" at a sufficiently positive level of correlation is equal to $p = 0.497$; "Fulfillment" on a high positive direct correlation is equal to $p = 0.743$; "Sexual satisfaction" on a high positive direct correlation is equal to $p = 0.622$.

Positive rather high correlations in three types of correlation analysis (Pearson, Kendall Tau and Spearman) give us the opportunity to say that the psychological well-being of businessmen depends on their sexual development and satisfaction with their sexual lives.

The obtained correlation data allow us to consider in more detail both age and gender characteristics, to investigate in more detail the levels of professional success of businessmen depending on their overall sexual satisfaction.

Conclusions

Theoretical and empirical analysis of modern approaches and research on the problem of satisfaction with one's own sexual life and the problem of psychological well-being of businessmen showed that sexual well-being of a person gives an opportunity to take a new approach to the study of psychological and emotional state of an entity in general and success of professional activities of businessmen in particular as components of development of personal maturity, increase of the potential in a professional business environment and prevention of stress and emotional burnout.

A study of the relationship between satisfaction with one's own sexual life and psychological well-being of businessmen, which was carried out using correlation analyses based on scientific developments of Pearson, Tau-b Kendall and Spearman enabled to reveal positive sufficiently high correlations in the three types of correlation analysis, which allows to state that psychological well-being of businessmen depends on their sexual fulfillment and on their level of satisfaction with their own sexual life.

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